

PROGRAMME
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An experimental study on methane and biogas oxy-flames under CO₂ dilution for CCUS applications

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Context

Source: International Energy Agency - WEO 2024

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Carbon capture – Oxycombustion with RFG

Objective

Analyze the effects of CO₂ addition in methane/oxygen long flame.

Tri-coaxial burner

Methane/oxygen flame detailed characterization under:

- Fuel CO₂ dilution (Biogas)
- Oxidizer CO₂ dilution (RFG)
- Constant equivalence ratio, ϕ and nominal power, P_N

Injection parameters

Fuel CO₂ content:

$$\beta = \frac{Q_{CO_2,f}}{Q_{CO_2,f} + Q_{CH_4}}$$

Oxidizer CO₂ dilution:

$$\alpha = \frac{Q_{CO_2,o}}{Q_{CO_2,o} + Q_{O_2}}$$

Oxygen distribution:

$$R_o = \frac{\dot{m}_{O_2,i}}{\dot{m}_{O_2,i} + \dot{m}_{O_2,e}}$$

Constant parameters

$$\phi = 0.95$$

$$P_N = 23kW$$

Experimental set up

Gas measurement and control

Control gas panel to obtain the different CH_4 , O_2 , and CO_2 mixtures

Chamber temperature profile

Thermocouples type K inserted 2.5 cm into the chamber wall

Exhaust gas composition measurements

- Ultramat 23 and Oxymat 61 gas Siemens analyzers
- Heated probe
- CO , NO_x , CO_2 , CH_4 and O_2

OH^* Chemiluminescence

- Camera: PI-MAX 4 emiCCD (1024 × 1024 pixels – 16 bits)
- Lens: f/2.8, 105 mm UV and UG11 filter

Experimental set up

10 kHz PIV

- Laser Nd:YAG 6 mJ/pulse at 532 nm
- Camera: Phantom V2012 with 180 mm
- Lens: Lens: f/2.8, 180 mm and 532 nm interference filter
- Seeding: ZrO₂ solid particles

10 kHz OH PLIF

- Sirah CREDO dye laser 0.1 mJ/pulse at 283 nm
- Camera: Phantom V2012 coupled with a fast intensifier
- Lens: f/2.8, 105 mm UV and UG11 filter

CO₂ dilution effects on the flame

Temperature profile

- Consistent temperature profiles for all the CO₂ dilution conditions
- The peak temperatures decrease with the increment in β and α

Flue gas measurements

- Nearly constant CO emissions for low and high α dilution values
- Dramatic CO increment near the limit case with a 1% α variation, for every β value

β (fuel)	0%				20%				50%			
α (oxidizer)	25%	60%	64%	65%	25%	60%	62%	63%	25%	50%	54%	55%
O ₂ [% vol]	9	3	3	3	7	3	3	3	6	4	4	4
CO ₂ [% vol]	89	95	95	95	90	95	95	94	92	94	94	94
CO [ppm @ 3% O ₂]	21	13	90	1800	13	14	238	1980	6	8	199	819
CH ₄ [ppm]	2	2	7	385	0	0	20	462	0	0	25	162
NO _x [mg/Nm ³ @ 3% O ₂]	23	7	7	8	9	7	7	7	4	4	4	5

— Low dilution

— Limit case

— High dilution

— Unstable flame

Flue gas measurements

- Nearly constant CO emissions for low and high α values
- Dramatic CO increment near the limit case, with a 1% α variation, for every β value
- Stability limits are found within a small range of total CO₂ [53.5% – 55.7%]

Flue gas measurements

- Nearly constant CO emissions for low and high α values
- Dramatic CO increment near the limit case, with a 1% α variation , for every β value
- Stability limits are found within a small range of total CO₂ [53.5% – 55.7%]
- The NOx concentrations (correspond to small air infiltration into the chamber) can be considered as ultra-low emissions for all the cases

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CO ₂ [% vol]	89	95	95	95	90	95	95	94	92	94	94	94
CO [ppm] at 3% O ₂	21	13	90	1800	17	14	238	1980	7	8	211	867
CH ₄ [ppm]	2	2	7	385	0	0	20	462	0	0	25	162
NOx [mg/Nm ³] at 3% O ₂	23	7	7	8	12	7	7	7	5	4	4	5

Nitrogen effect on the biogas

What impact have the presence of N₂ in the biogas?

β	50%				
d_{N_2}	0%	2%	4%	6%	8%
O ₂ [% vol]	6	6	6	6	6
CO ₂ [% vol]	92	92	92	92	92
CO [ppm at 3% O ₂]	14	16	17	18	20
CH ₄ [ppm]	1	1	2	3	12
NOx [mg/Nm ³ at 3% O ₂]	25	30	37	44	62

$\alpha = 25\%$
 $\phi = 0.95$
 d_{N_2} = Nitrogen dilution of the fuel

$$d_{N_2} = \frac{Q_{N_2}}{Q_{N_2} + Q_{CO_2,f}}$$

- The NOx emissions increase with the presence of nitrogen on the fuel
- The NOx production remains low

Flame imaging by OH* Chemiluminescence

- Two main regions :
 - high heat release zone near the burner → pilot-like flame
 - lower intensity → long main diffusion flame

Flame imaging by OH* Chemiluminescence

- Two main regions :
 - high heat release zone near the burner → pilot-like flame
 - lower intensity → long main diffusion flame
- Increasing the CO₂ in the oxidizer reduces the heat release intensity of the main diffusion flame
- Increasing the CO₂ in the fuel reduces the heat release intensity of the pilot flame

β = CO₂ in fuel
 α = CO₂ in oxidizer

$$\beta = 0; \alpha = 65\%$$

Synchronized 10 kHz PIV and OH PLIF

Count of extinction events with High speed OH PLIF

- Higher flame presence near the burner due to the pilot-like flame
- More extinction events observed with the increment of α , coherent with augmented CO production

- Consistent temperature profiles for all dilution cases:
 - Low temperature near the burner
 - Maximal temperature in $Z=750$ mm
- Near constant CO emissions with a significant increase for high CO₂ diluted flames in unstable cases.
- Minimal NO_x emissions corresponding to small air infiltrations.
- Heat release intensity reduction with CO₂ dilution:
 - On the main diffusion flame for oxidizer
 - On the pilot flame for the fuel
- Advanced laser diagnostics allows a further understanding on the stability limits of CO₂ diluted oxy-flames.
- Biogas oxy-combustion with RFG has been shown to be an effective method of producing heat under a wide range of CO₂ dilutions, making it a potential method for CCS.

Thank you for your
attention

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